

Numerical investigation of sorption-enhanced ammonia synthesis for hydrogen storage: CFD modeling, experimental validation, and scale-up

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ABSTRACT

Ammonia (NH₃) is increasingly recognized as a clean hydrogen (H₂) carrier due to its high H₂ content, carbon neutrality, and ease of storage and transport. Realizing its potential as an energy vector requires synthesis technologies that operate under mild conditions and are compatible with water electrolysis. This study develops a comprehensive computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model of sorption-enhanced NH₃ synthesis with alternating catalyst and sorbent layers, validated against experimental data, to elucidate the in-situ sorption effects. The model is subsequently employed to scale up the process and to optimize the operation conditions of a pilot-scale reactor. Results indicate a 66.8% increase in H₂ conversion with a six-layer configuration, while a 60-layer pilot reactor achieves over 90% conversion and 99.5% NH₃ capture in single-pass operation. These findings demonstrate the scalability and potential of sorption-enhanced NH₃ synthesis, providing a moderate and efficient pathway for H₂ storage and transport.

1. Introduction

Ammonia (NH₃) is a crucial chemical with extensive applications in agriculture, chemistry, pharmaceuticals, and energy that have been established for a long time, playing a significant role in advancing modern society [1]. Recently, the use of NH₃ in the energy sector, particularly for energy storage, has been continuously increasing through the Power-to-X (PtX) pathway [2], which converts renewable energy into hydrogen (H₂) via water electrolysis or further into synthetic fuels such as methanol or NH₃ by integrating the synthesis process of the demanding electro-fuel [3]. The favorable properties of NH₃, including high hydrogen content, high energy density, ease of storage and transportation, and carbon-free nature, make it an ideal H₂ carrier [4,5]. Consequently, NH₃ is considered one of the most promising carriers for final products in the PtX pathway [6], addressing the storage and transport challenges of green H₂ [7]. Recent progress in employing NH₃ as the energy carrier to realize the Power-to-Ammonia (PtA) path has demonstrated highly promising results, significantly enhancing the demand and potential of NH₃ in the energy sector [8].

However, integrating green H₂ production systems with conventional NH₃ synthesis, namely the Haber–Bosch (HB) process, poses significant challenges. The traditional HB process is typically centralized, relying on hydrogen from steam methane reforming based on

fossil fuels such as natural gas or coal, therefore making intensive carbon emissions [9]. This is due to the harsh operating conditions required (400–500 °C, 150–300 bar) [10], making it economically viable only for centralized forms and preferable with a stable and continuous hydrogen supply [11]. Current HB plants produce up to 3300 tons of NH₃ per day [12]. In contrast, green hydrogen systems are typically designed for smaller-scale, distributed deployment alongside renewable power generation, further emphasizing the need for efficient storage and transportation solutions. To integrate NH₃ production with green hydrogen generation, synthesis units must be downscaled to capacities of 3–60 tons per day [13]. Additionally, hydrogen production is inherently intermittent and dynamic due to the variable nature of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind [14]. Consequently, the NH₃ synthesis process must be both downscaled and adaptable to fluctuating operating conditions to effectively integrate with water electrolysis systems [15], thereby realizing NH₃ as a viable carrier for H₂ storage and transport. As mentioned earlier, downscaling the HB unit requires reducing its operating conditions while maintaining a satisfactory NH₃ synthesis rate. While, synthesizing NH₃ under milder conditions is facing challenges.

The first major challenge is the low NH₃ yield rate under mild conditions, as the most commonly used catalysts exhibit low activity

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at reduced temperatures, limiting the production rate [16]. This is due to the strong $N\equiv N$ bond of nitrogen (N_2), which normally requires a high temperature to overcome the energy barrier for the bond cleavage [17]. Developing highly active catalysts or employing auxiliary methods to activate N_2 and thereby enhance the NH_3 synthesis rate are the two main strategies for mild-condition synthesis [18]. Fundamentally, the research on catalytic materials is centered on understanding and enhancing N_2 activation. According to the Sabatier principle, an optimal catalyst must balance adsorption and desorption-binding reactants strongly enough to activate them while allowing products to desorb efficiently, leading to the well-known volcano-type relationship between catalytic activity and metal–nitrogen bond strength [19]. Traditional Fe-based catalysts lie below the optimum on this curve, whereas transition metals such as ruthenium (Ru) and molybdenum (Mo) exhibit superior intrinsic activity [20], highlighting the potential for enhanced performance under milder conditions. In addition, promoters such as alkali or potassium (K) can beneficially modify the structural and electronic properties of the catalyst, further improving N_2 adsorption and activation [21]. The state-of-the-art for novel catalyst design incorporating noble metal-based, support and promoters, and other innovative materials, is reviewed in [22].

Another significant obstacle is separating NH_3 synthesized under reduced pressure [23]. The conventional physical condensation method, commonly used for separating NH_3 in HB units, becomes inefficient at low NH_3 partial pressures [24], particularly for cases with low NH_3 yield. Therefore, alternative NH_3 separation techniques are required to align the synthesis process with mild operating conditions [25]. Recent studies suggest that absorption-enhanced ammonia synthesis processes are promising for addressing both challenges simultaneously. On one hand, in-situ absorption can effectively enhance the synthesis rate by shifting the equilibrium [26]. The NH_3 produced is immediately captured by co-loaded absorbents using either mixed or layered configurations, thus exceeding the equilibrium limitations under specific conditions. Additionally, the kinetic rate is improved due to its positive correlation with H_2 and N_2 fractions and negative correlation with NH_3 fraction [27]. On the other hand, this approach also simplifies NH_3 separation and storage, eliminating the need for an additional condensation process [28]. Absorbents such as metal halides exhibit strong sorption capabilities under very low partial pressures of NH_3 (0.01 bar) and are reversible, effectively acting as NH_3 capacitors in the process [24]. Consequently, the integrated NH_3 synthesis and sorption process has attracted increasing attention [29,30].

For example, Ojha et al. demonstrated an integrated NH_3 synthesis and separation process within a single vessel operating at 400 °C and 27 bar, utilizing an Fe-based catalyst in conjunction with a nickel chloride ($NiCl_2$) absorbent [31]. This approach achieved a synthesis rate comparable to traditional methods. Additionally, the study revealed that $NiCl_2$ exhibits superior NH_3 uptake performance at very low pressures compared to magnesium chloride ($MgCl_2$). Nowrin et al. have comparatively investigated sorption-enhanced NH_3 synthesis using in-situ and ex-situ absorption in two separate reactors, both with and without a recycling strategy [32]. An NH_3 production rate of up to 27 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{g}_{\text{cat.}}/\text{s}$ was achieved, underscoring the feasibility of NH_3 production at pressures as low as 30 bar in the presence of calcium chloride ($CaCl_2$) absorbent. Moreover, the process demonstrated stable performance across multiple cycles without significant degradation of the absorbent's efficiency, highlighting the potential for continuous operation using this configuration. Furthermore, Smith et al. have reported a study on such an integrated system employing a layer-by-layer configuration of catalysts and absorbents [26]. A series of experiments were conducted using manganese chloride ($MnCl_2$) as the sorbent and Ru as the catalyst, exploring temperature variations from 250 °C to 400 °C, changes in reactant ratios, and the effects of the number of layers. The results demonstrate that sorption-enhanced synthesis has the potential to exceed equilibrium limitations in a single pass, with an increased number of layers significantly enhancing this effect. These

findings confirm that mild NH_3 synthesis using an integrated catalyst and sorbent reactor is feasible, though uncertainties remain such as chloridic acid formation due to the hydrophilic nature of the metal halide.

Apart from thermocatalytic technology, recent progress in other alternative mild-condition NH_3 synthesis strategies has also gained attention. Plasma-assisted synthesis enables N_2 and H_2 activation under ambient conditions, and the use of dielectric barrier discharge plasma allows for simple reactor construction and operation [33]. However, this approach remains limited by low NH_3 yield and poor energy efficiency, as a substantial portion of input energy is lost to non-productive plasma excitation and partial NH_3 decomposition by high-energy electrons. Moreover, scaling up plasma reactors to industrially relevant throughputs is challenging due to nonuniform plasma distribution and power density constraints [34]. Membrane-assisted reactors represent another promising pathway by integrating NH_3 synthesis and separation within a single unit, where selective permeation drives the reaction beyond equilibrium. While this configuration can improve energy efficiency at the reactor level, the scalability is constrained by membrane material durability, fabrication cost, and the complexity of maintaining high selectivity under elevated pressures and temperatures [35]. In contrast, the sorption-enhanced thermocatalytic process offers an inherently scalable and energy-efficient alternative. A more comprehensive review and comparison of these emerging strategies in terms of energy efficiency and scalability are provided in [22].

Despite these advancements, most reported studies have been conducted at micro or lab scales. Upscaling the integrated configuration remains largely unexplored but is essential to address. To design and virtually test pilot-scale reactors, modeling and simulation tools are indispensable, with computational fluid dynamics (CFD) being particularly effective for providing comprehensive and detailed results as well as straightforward visualization [36]. Currently, there are limited CFD modeling studies on mildly NH_3 thermocatalytic synthesis that incorporate catalytic reactions, heat and mass transfer, and fluid flow in the literature [37]. A CFD model specifically for an integrated NH_3 synthesis and absorption reactor has yet to be developed. Studies on the design and optimization of pilot-scale NH_3 synthesis–sorption integrated reactors remain scarce.

In this study, we investigate the scalability and operational characteristics of an integrated NH_3 synthesis–sorption process within a single vessel. The novelty of this study lies in the integration of experimentally validated kinetic models for both ammonia synthesis and sorption into a unified, transient CFD framework, enabling detailed analysis of coupled reaction–absorption phenomena under realistic flow and thermal conditions. Unlike previous works that focused primarily on either small-scale experimental demonstrations or simplified reactor models, this study extends the investigation to a multi-layer configuration and performs a full-scale numerical scale-up to a pilot reactor, revealing how in-situ NH_3 removal dynamically shifts equilibrium and enhances conversion beyond conventional limits. The reactor's performance is analyzed across both time and spatial dimensions to identify the optimal batch time until absorbents regeneration. Finally, a parametric study is carried out to examine the effects of pressure and temperature on NH_3 production, providing insights into the upscaling of NH_3 synthesis–sorption integrated reactor.

2. Modeling description

This work develops a comprehensive CFD model that integrates the kinetics of NH_3 synthesis and sorption with heat and mass transfer, as well as single-phase flow through the porous media formed by loading catalyst and sorbent in a layered configuration. The subsequent sections detail the incorporated kinetic models and the overall CFD modeling framework.

2.1. Kinetic models

2.1.1. Synthesis kinetic model

Commercial iron (Fe)-based catalysts are predominantly used for ammonia synthesis due to their high performance in terms of efficiency and economic feasibility under high-temperature and high-pressure conditions [10]. In contrast, ruthenium (Ru)-based catalysts are generally recognized for their superior activation under milder conditions, such as within the temperature range of 350–400 °C, though their economic cost is significantly higher [38]. However, a previous study has demonstrated that the commercial Fe-based KATALCO 74-1 catalyst exhibits superior activity below 300 °C compared to ruthenium and caesium supported on ceria when evaluated on a mass basis [39]. This finding highlights that Fe-based catalysts are not only effective under high-temperature conditions but also hold potential for ammonia synthesis under milder conditions. In this study, the Fe-based catalyst is selected for the reactor design, with the purpose of enabling ammonia synthesis at 300 °C with cost-efficient materials. The properties and experimental performance of the catalyst are referenced from [39]. Consequently, the global kinetic model for Fe-catalysts, i.e., Temkin model, is used to predict the synthesis rate over Fe-catalyst due to its reliability and robustness. The global reaction of the catalytic synthesis is as follows [37].

The corresponding synthesis rate of NH_3 is written as [27]:

$$R_{\text{NH}_3} = 2k \left(k_a^2 a_{\text{N}_2} \left[\frac{(a_{\text{H}_2})^3}{(a_{\text{NH}_3})^2} \right]^\alpha - \left[\frac{(a_{\text{NH}_3})^2}{(a_{\text{H}_2})^2} \right]^{1-\alpha} \right) \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{m}^3\text{hr}} \quad (2)$$

where α is an empirical constant (0.5 or 0.75), 0.5 used in this study, k denotes the reaction rate constant, k_a indicates the equilibrium constant, a_i represents the activity of i component ($i = \text{H}_2, \text{N}_2, \text{NH}_3$) [40]. More detailed description of the Temkin model refers to [27].

2.1.2. Absorption kinetic model

Metal halides have been selected as promising candidates for ammonia absorption due to their high sorption capacity, excellent reversibility, economic viability, and thermal stability, demonstrating significant potential for in-situ ammonia separation [41]. Among these, MgCl_2 is recognized for its superior absorption capacity [42]. However, its practical application is hindered by challenges such as corrosion risks and high hydrophilicity [43]. In contrast, MnCl_2 exhibits better stability compared to MgCl_2 while maintaining a high sorption capacity relative to other absorbents [26]. Consequently, MnCl_2 is selected as the absorbent in this study to investigate the integrated process of ammonia synthesis and sorption. The semi-empirical kinetic model for MnCl_2 sorption is developed in [26], in which the sorption process is divided into three steps, i.e., the adsorption process (1st step) and two chemical sorption steps (2nd and 3rd steps), as shown below.

The overall sorption rate in terms of $\text{mol/g}_{\text{MnCl}_2}\text{min}$ can be written as:

$$R_{\text{sorp.}} = 3 \times 10^{-4} (P_{\text{NH}_3} - 0.05)(1 - X_A^1) + 2 \times 10^{-2} (P_{\text{NH}_3} - P_{\text{eq1}})^4 (1 - X_A^2)^4 + 2.5 \times 10^{-2} (P_{\text{NH}_3} - P_{\text{eq2}})^4 (1 - X_A^3)^6 \quad (5)$$

This overall process is hereafter referred to as ‘‘sorption’’ to distinguish it from adsorption (1st term) and absorption (2nd and 3rd terms). P_{NH_3} denotes the partial pressure of ammonia with the unit of bar, P_{eq1} and P_{eq2} represent the equilibrium pressures for the 2nd step and 3rd step, respectively. X_A^k indicates the fraction of sorption capacity reached in each step, 13% of a molar equivalent of MnCl_2 for adsorption step and 35% molar equivalent for the other two bulk sorption steps. More detailed description and validation of the model refer to [26].

Fig. 1. Configuration of the CFD modeling reactor with two layers.

2.2. CFD framework

The transient CFD model for the layer-by-layer configuration, illustrated in Fig. 1 (two-layer case), was developed in ANSYS Fluent 2023 R1 under the following assumptions.

- The gas mixture only consists of three main species (H_2 , N_2 and NH_3), intermediate species, radicals, were neglected and all treated as ideal gases.
- The properties of gas species and mixture are governed by ideal gas law.
- Only the global NH_3 synthesis reaction is taken into account in the catalyst layer [37].
- Porous zones loading catalyst and sorbent are isotropic with uniform porosity and particle size.
- Potential interactions between catalyst and sorbent at the contact interface are not taken into account.
- The porous zones are assumed to be in thermal equilibrium, sharing the same energy equation.

The kinetic models and reaction heats (-84200 J/mol for absorption [44]) are implemented via user-defined expressions (UDEs) in ANSYS Fluent [45]. The fraction of capacity reached (X_A^k) for each sorption step is computed using a user-defined scalar (UDS), which is coupled with the implicit absorption kinetic model defined by UDEs [46]. The general transport equation (except the energy transport equation) solved in the developed CFD model for the reactive, single-phase flow porous zones is described below [45].

$$\frac{\partial(\epsilon \rho_f \phi)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_f \vec{v} \phi) = \nabla \cdot (\epsilon \Gamma \nabla \phi) + \epsilon S_\phi \quad (6)$$

The pressure drop in the porous medium is accounted for by introducing an additional source term into the momentum equation, expressed as follows [47]:

$$S_i = - \left(\sum D_{ij} \mu v_j + \sum C_{ij} \frac{1}{2} \rho_f |v| v_j \right) \quad (7)$$

where S_i is the source term for the i_{th} (x, y, z) momentum equation, D and C denote the prescribed matrices viscous resistance and inertial resistance, respectively. For homogeneous porous media, the source term can be simplified into:

$$S_i = - \left(\frac{\mu v_i}{\alpha} + C_2 \frac{1}{2} \rho_f |v| v_i \right) \quad (8)$$

where α denotes the permeability and C_2 represents the inertial resistance factor. These two parameters for the packed bed can be estimated by the semi-empirical correlation, i.e., Ergun equation (Blake–Kozeny equation for laminar flow), as follows [47].

$$\alpha = \frac{D_p^2}{150} \frac{\epsilon^3}{(1 - \epsilon)^2} \quad (9)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{3.5}{D_p} \frac{(1 - \epsilon)}{\epsilon^3} \quad (10)$$

The parameters D_p and ϵ refer to the particle size and porosity of the porous zone. The lumped energy transport equation for the thermal

Table 1
Summary of the numerical methods used in this CFD model.

Items	Model or Numerical method used
Model type	3D/2D transient non-isothermal model
Catalyst bed	Fe-catalyst with 2700 kg/m ³ density, 2 mm average diameter and 0.5 porosity [39]
Absorbent bed	MnCl ₂ absorbent with 600 kg/m ³ density, 1 mm average diameter and 0.5 porosity [26]
Fluid flow	Laminar reacting flow with inlet Reynolds number below 1000, enabling species transport
Chemical reactions	Global reaction of NH ₃ synthesis Eq. (1); NH ₃ absorption Eqs. (3) and (4)
Kinetic models	The modified Temkin model for NH ₃ synthesis [27]; Smith's model for NH ₃ absorption [26]
Boundary conditions	Velocity inlet, outflow outlet, iso-thermal boundary for walls
Numerical methods	Coupled algorithm; second order upwind scheme for discretization.
Solver	ANSYS Fluent 2023 R1.

equilibrium porous media is described as follows.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\varepsilon \rho_f E_f + (1-\varepsilon) \rho_s E_s) + \nabla \cdot (\vec{v}(\rho_f E_f + p)) = S_f^h + \nabla \cdot \left[k_{eff} \nabla T - \sum_i h_i J_i + \vec{\tau} \cdot \vec{v} \right] \quad (11)$$

Here E_f and E_s stands for the total fluid energy and solid energy, respectively. S_f^h represents the fluid enthalpy source term, and k_{eff} denotes the effective thermal conductivity of the medium, calculated as the weighted sum of thermal conductivities of the fluid and solid phases.

It is worth noting that the model assumptions and kinetic models used may influence the quantitative accuracy of the simulation results. The kinetic parameters adopted from literature sources are subject to experimental conditions and uncertainties, particularly for the sorption model, where data variability in reaction constants and equilibrium pressures can affect predicted absorption rates. Furthermore, the model neglects intermediate species and radical reactions, assuming that ammonia synthesis can be represented by a single global reaction. While this assumption is widely applied for reactor-scale modeling, it may underestimate localized kinetic effects near active sites. The use of the ideal gas law and isotropic porous media properties also introduces approximations, which may lead to minor deviations under high-pressure conditions. Nevertheless, these simplifications were necessary to achieve computational tractability for the large-scale transient CFD simulations and do not affect the overall qualitative trends and conclusions drawn from this study. The key models and numerical methods used in this CFD framework are summarized in Table 1.

3. Model validation

3.1. Ammonia synthesis model validation

To validate the reliability of the CFD model for predicting NH₃ synthesis process, the 3D simulation results, after a grid convergence study as reported in [48], are compared with the experimental data originally presented in [49]. The simulations were conducted under the identical experimental conditions in [49] for the first 8 cases presented in Table 2, where the absorbent bed was disabled for all simulations. As presented in Fig. 2, CFD model results align well with the experimental trends in y_{NH_3} along the length of the catalyst bed for the chosen ranges of inlet temperatures and pressures. The following statistical analysis confirms the agreement between experimental and model results ($R^2 > 0.90$) for the majority of the simulation cases. However, some discrepancies remain, particularly at 45 barg where kinetic and transport limitations are more pronounced. Experimental uncertainties such as feed composition, reactor packing, temperature

Table 2

Initial conditions used in CFD simulations for NH₃ synthesis model validation.

Case	Temperature, °C	Pressure, barg	H ₂ /N ₂ , vol.	Sorbent
1	300	10	3	None
2	300	45	3	None
3	350	10	3	None
4	350	45	3	None
5	300	10	1	None
6	300	45	1	None
7	350	10	1	None
8	350	45	1	None
9	280	20	3	MnCl ₂
10	300	20	3	MnCl ₂
11	320	20	3	MnCl ₂
12	340	20	3	MnCl ₂

control, and instrument calibration may also contribute to deviations. Overall, the CFD results align well with literature experimental data with minor deviations, supporting the validity of the implemented NH₃ synthesis kinetic model.

3.2. Ammonia absorption model validation

To validate the NH₃ absorption kinetic model implemented in the CFD framework, the NH₃ removal rate values predicted by the model were compared with the experimental data reported in [26] under the same conditions, i.e., the last four cases (9–12) stated in Table 2. As shown in Fig. 3, the NH₃ absorption rate over time declines, as the absorbent loses its capacity, which is observed from both experimental data and CFD model results. First 3 min were removed from the simulation data set for better agreement with experimental data, as the absorption kinetic model does not account for dispersion [26]. The curve corresponding to the kinetic model in Fig. 3 represents the calculated NH₃ removal behavior based solely on the intrinsic kinetic expressions and initial boundary conditions, without accounting for heat and mass transfer effects. The slight deviations between the two curves therefore arise from mass diffusion limitations, thermal distributions and nonuniform concentration fields captured only in the CFD simulation. Overall, the model shows strong agreement with the experimental data in all 4 cases. However, some discrepancies can be observed most likely due to the complexity of the actual absorption process, that cannot be fully captured in the kinetic model. For instance, NH₃ diffusion within individual absorbent particles can influence the absorption rate, and structural inhomogeneities in the experimental absorbent may cause certain particles to saturate faster. Nevertheless, the simulation results align well with the experimental data, which confirms the reliability of the implemented NH₃ absorption kinetic

Fig. 2. NH_3 molar fraction along the catalyst bed comparing experimental results from [49] and CFD model developed in this study for: (a) $T = 300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{H}_2/\text{N}_2 = 3$; (b) $T = 300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{H}_2/\text{N}_2 = 1$; (c) $T = 350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{H}_2/\text{N}_2 = 3$; (d) $T = 350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{H}_2/\text{N}_2 = 1$.

model for the chosen range of the inlet parameters and justifies the model assumptions.

3.3. Dimensionality reduction validation

Due to the presence of the absorbent, the process is highly dynamic. The transient simulation of the reactor is therefore desired, which increases the computational cost significantly. Considering the symmetry of the reactor vessel and to reduce computational burden, the 3D model is simplified to 2D while maintaining the same space velocity for the catalytic reaction. A comparison of the 2D and 3D simulation results shows identical values up to four significant digits, confirming the validity of the dimensionality reduction. Moreover, the 2D simulation results were further compared with experimental data from [39], which were obtained using the same Fe-based KATALCO 74-1 catalyst under identical operating conditions (low temperature). As shown in Fig. 4, the simulated hydrogen conversion exhibits good agreement with the experimental measurements across various temperatures (250 °C, 275 °C, and 300 °C). However, a slightly larger discrepancy was observed in the ammonia synthesis rate at 250 °C and 300 °C, likely due to the sensitivity of the reaction rate calculations. Overall, the simulation results align well with the experimental data, confirming the reliability of the model for predicting ammonia production in this configuration under mild conditions.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Analysis of the 2-layer reactor

After model validation, the effect of in-situ absorption on ammonia synthesis is examined by comparing cases with and without sorption in

the 2-layer configuration under 300 °C and 40 bar. Fig. 5 presents the NH_3 outlet fraction over time for both scenarios. The results indicate that, in the absence of absorption, the system reaches steady state after approximately 400 s, when the relative change of the NH_3 outlet fraction within one second is less than 0.001%, yielding an NH_3 outlet concentration of 2.17 vol.%. In contrast, with absorption enabled, the system remains far from steady state even after 1200 s. The majority of the synthesized ammonia is captured by the absorbent, resulting in only 0.5 vol.% NH_3 at the outlet, a reduction of 77.22% compared to the non-absorbent case. Additionally, the NH_3 outlet fraction gradually increases over time as the absorbents approach their uptake capacity. Consequently, the absorbed NH_3 fraction, defined as the ratio of NH_3 trapped in the sorbent to the total produced NH_3 (sum of trapped and outlet NH_3), decreases from near 100% to 78.16% over the course of the reaction, highlighting a reduction of the practical performance of the absorbents during the reactor operation.

Fig. 6 presents the NH_3 mass fraction contours inside the reactor for the non-absorbent case at 400 s (a) and for the absorbent case at 400 s (b), 800 s (c), and 1200 s (d). Fig. 6(a) clearly illustrates the NH_3 distribution within the reactor at steady state when only the synthesis process is considered, showing that the NH_3 fraction remains nearly constant downstream of the catalyst bed. In contrast, the other three subfigures reveal significant NH_3 fraction gradients along the reactor length for the cases with absorbent loading. The NH_3 fraction is substantially reduced as the flow passes through the absorbent bed, leading to a lower NH_3 outlet fraction. In Fig. 6(d), the concentration gradient along the absorbent bed, decreasing from the catalyst bed concentration to a lower level, demonstrates the practical absorption performance after 1200 s of operation. This indicates that the absorbents closest to the catalyst bed have already reached saturation.

Fig. 3. NH₃ removal over time comparing experimental results from [26] and CFD model developed in this study for: (a) $T = 280\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, (b) $T = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, (c) $T = 320\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, (d) $T = 340\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the 2D simulation modeling results with experimental data from [39].

Fig. 5. Profiles of NH₃ outlet fraction and absorbed fraction for 2 layers reactor: with absorption vs. non-absorption.

4.2. Reactor scale-up to multiple layers

To further investigate the configuration of alternating catalyst-sorbent loading, two additional small-scale reactors with 4 and 6 layers, as illustrated in Fig. 7, were simulated and comparatively analyzed. The catalyst bed length was kept constant at 17.5 mm, while the sorbent bed length decreased to 76.9 mm and 75.7 mm for the second and third sorbent layers, respectively. These values were determined from thermodynamic calculations, assuming a constant sorption capacity of 40 mg/g_{sorb.}, sufficient to completely remove the NH₃ produced, and an identical conversion rate across each catalyst bed. As the reactant flow rate decreases through successive catalyst beds, the required sorbent amount correspondingly diminishes. The comparative analysis of the 4-layer and 6-layer reactors provides further insight into the effects of in-situ sorption and the performance of multi-layer reactor configurations.

Fig. 8(a) provides a comparative analysis of the impact of sorption on conversion over flow time across different layer-number configurations. In cases where the absorption model is enabled, the conversion is consistently higher than in the corresponding cases without absorption, clearly demonstrating the promotion effect of in-situ sorption on NH₃ synthesis. This confirms that in-situ sorption enhances conversion by locally shifting the reaction equilibrium, thereby increasing NH₃ production. The conversions of H₂ for all simulated cases initially start at 100% (due to zero H₂ at the outlet in the beginning) and gradually decline, stabilizing at nearly constant values after approximately 450 s, for example, 13.95%, 9.27%, and 4.58% for the 6-layer, 4-layer, and 2-layer configurations with absorption, respectively. This indicates a nearly linear increase in H₂ conversion with the number of catalyst beds after reaching a quasi-steady state, thanks to the effective removal of NH₃ with the presence of sorbents. In contrast, for the cases without absorption, the increase in conversion with the number of catalyst beds is significantly nonlinear, showing 4.25%, 6.55%, and 8.28% conversion for the 2-layer, 4-layer, and 6-layer configurations, respectively.

Fig. 6. Contours of NH_3 mass fraction for 2 layers reactor at different time points.

Fig. 7. Configuration of the 4-layer and 6-layer reactors.

Fig. 8. Conversion profile comparison: with absorption vs. non-absorption (a) and conversion increment (b), for the reactors with 2, 4 and 6 layer numbers.

Moreover, this promotion effect due to absorption becomes more pronounced as the number of layers increases, as further quantified in Fig. 8(b). For instance, at 500 s, the relative conversion increments due to the absorption effect (compared to NH_3 yield without sorption) for the 2-layer, 4-layer, and 6-layer configurations are 7.24%, 40.23%, and 66.80%, respectively. This effect is attributed to the continuous removal of NH_3 from the reaction zone, which mitigates equilibrium limitations and facilitates higher reactant conversion into ammonia. This enhancement is driven not only by convection but also by diffusion-mediated sorption in adjacent absorbent layers. Therefore, increasing the number of alternating catalyst and absorbent layers leads to greater enhancements in the synthesis process. It is reasonable to conclude that, with a sufficient number of catalyst-absorbent layers, the NH_3 synthesis process can exceed conventional equilibrium limits, achieving the target conversion in a single pass. This finding highlights the critical role of absorbents in enhancing ammonia synthesis efficiency and underscores the necessity and synergistic effect of using multiple catalyst-absorbent layers.

Fig. 9 compares NH_3 productivity and absorption behavior over a 1200 s operation period for the three configurations with absorption enabled. A nearly linear increase in NH_3 production flux is observed as the number of reactor layers increases. After 400 s, the three NH_3 production flux curves become almost parallel, following the same gradual decreasing trend, further confirming that the reaction process approaches a quasi-steady state. The slight decline in NH_3 productivity

Fig. 9. Comparison of NH_3 production and absorption for the reactors with 2, 4 and 6 layer numbers with enabling absorption.

over time is attributed to the progressive saturation of the absorbents, which diminishes their promotion effect on the synthesis process. This is further supported by the trends in NH_3 absorbed fraction in Fig. 9, which continuously decrease from near 100%, illustrating both the saturation of a portion of the absorbents and the gradual reduction

Fig. 10. Contours of mass fractions of NH_3 , H_2 and N_2 and the user-defined scalars inside the 6-layer reactor after 3000 s.

in overall sorption performance. At 1200 s, the absorbed NH_3 fractions for the 6-layer, 4-layer, and 2-layer configurations are 93.47%, 89.47%, and 78.16%, respectively, with corresponding NH_3 productivities of 0.0463, 0.0318, and 0.0172 $\text{kg}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$. These data provide a valuable basis for optimizing reactor batch operation periods and guiding absorbent regeneration strategies.

Fig. 10 presents a detailed spacial analysis for the 6-layer configuration, illustrating the distributions of mass fractions of NH_3 , H_2 and N_2 , and the three user-defined scalars (UDSs) representing the capacity-reached index for each sorption step inside the reactor after 3000 s of operation. NH_3 is primarily concentrated in the three catalyst zones and exhibits decreasing gradients toward the adjacent absorbent zones due to the combined effects of absorption and gas diffusion. The NH_3 fraction in the third bed is higher than in the other two, as unabsorbed NH_3 from upstream beds is transported downstream by convection. The mass fractions of H_2 and N_2 show an inverse distribution trend relative to NH_3 , with lower values in the catalyst zones and higher values elsewhere, reflecting the stoichiometric supply of H_2 and N_2 from the inlet. The area-averaged mass fractions of NH_3 , H_2 and N_2 at the outlet are 2.50%, 17.31% and 80.19%, respectively, corresponding to the molar fractions of 1.27%, 74.05% and 24.68%.

In the absorbent zones, UDS-0 has reached its maximum value (0.13), indicating that the first sorption step (adsorption) has reached full capacity. In contrast, the two subsequent absorption steps are still active, as UDS-1 and UDS-2 remain below their respective limit values (0.35). However, in the second sorption step (UDS-1), the absorbents near the catalyst zone are approaching saturation, whereas the third sorption step (UDS-2) has not yet been initiated for absorbents further from the catalyst beds. This observation confirms that, at the current stage, the second sorption step primarily governs NH_3 uptake, while the NH_3 partial pressure remains too low to fully trigger the third sorption step across all absorbent zones.

4.3. Scale-up to pilot reactor

The preceding sections demonstrate the effectiveness of employing additional alternating layers of catalyst and sorbent to enhance conversion, but the reactors still remain at small scale. To achieve sufficiently high conversion (e.g., >90%) in a single pass and thereby eliminate the need for recycling, the process is further scaled up to pilot scale in this section. Thermodynamic calculations indicate that a single-pass conversion of 90% can be achieved with 60 alternating layers of

Fig. 11. Configuration of the pilot reactor with 60 beds of catalyst and absorbent.

Fig. 12. Profile of conversion, NH_3 production, absorbed fraction and outlet fraction for the pilot reactor under 40 bar and 300 °C.

catalyst and sorbent at 300 °C and 40 bar, constrained by the assumed sorption capacity (40 mg/g_{sorb.}) The configuration of the pilot reactor is depicted in Fig. 11, where the catalyst bed length remains constant at 17.5 mm, while the absorbent bed length decreases progressively from 77.7 mm in the first bed to 33.5 mm in the last bed. The inner diameter of the vessel is 29.5 mm, aligning with the engineering demand. The detailed lengths of each absorbent layer are provided in Appendix A.

4.3.1. Pilot-scale simulation analysis

Fig. 12 presents the profiles of conversion, NH_3 outlet fraction, NH_3 absorbed fraction, and NH_3 production flux over time. The conversion curve declines from an initial value of close to 100% to the target conversion of 90% within 3676 s, which can be considered the batch operation period of the pilot reactor. In other words, the reactor should be shut down after 3676 s, at which point 99.51% of the produced NH_3 is absorbed, yielding an NH_3 production flux of 0.326 kg/m₂/s, with only 1.31% escaping at the outlet. This demonstrates good performance, achieving the target conversion in a single pass while storing most of the produced NH_3 in the absorbents within approximately one hour of operation. In this period, the highest NH_3 production flux occurs at 2462 s, coinciding with a critical point where H_2 conversion begins to decline rapidly. This is likely due to a decrease in adsorption ability at this time point due to its rapidness and low capacity, leading to a reduction in the NH_3 synthesis rate.

The contours of H_2 and NH_3 mass fractions, and the three defined scalars inside the pilot reactor are displayed in Fig. 13. H_2 fraction decreases along the flow direction in the reactor, owing to the synthesis process and removal of NH_3 produced. The NH_3 distribution exhibits alternating peaks and valleys in the catalyst and absorbent zones, with a maximum mass fraction of 5.88% observed in the downstream catalyst zones. The outlet NH_3 mass fraction decreases to 1.44%, due to the sufficiently active absorbents in the final absorbent zones. This behavior is further confirmed by the distributions of the three defined scalars, which indicate that the adsorption step (Fig. 13(c)) has reached saturation, while the chemisorption steps (Fig. 13(d–e)) are still effectively functioning. However, the third absorption step, which requires a higher NH_3 partial pressure, is largely inactive for most absorbents, occurring only in narrow regions adjacent to the catalyst beds and the downstream absorbent layers. Combining these findings with the results in Fig. 12, it is reasonable to conclude that the second absorption

step dominates the absorption process from 2462 s to 3676 s. Under the working conditions of 40 bar and 300 °C, corresponding to an NH_3 mass fraction of approximately 3.6% to sufficiently trigger the third absorption step. If the reactor continues operation beyond 3676 s, the accumulation of produced NH_3 will increase its partial pressure, thereby activating the third absorption step. However, this would also result in a lower conversion (below 90%) for an extended operation period.

4.3.2. Pressure parametric study

Fig. 14 presents the results of a parametric study that quantitatively investigates the impact of operating pressure on conversion, varying the pressure from 20 bar to 50 bar in increments of 5 bar. All simulations are conducted over a two-hour period under identical conditions, except for the variation in pressure, with H_2 conversion recorded every 2 s, resulting in the profiles plotted in Fig. 14(a). A substantial variation is observed among the conversion profiles under different pressures. Sharp decreases within the first 1500 s are evident for the cases at lower pressures (20, 25, and 30 bar), indicating a very short batch operation time if the reactor still targets a 90% conversion. Considering the transport time from the inlet to the outlet in such a long reactor, operating conditions below 30 bar are deemed unsuitable. For cases at or above 35 bar, the time required to reach 90% conversion is significantly extended, and the decreasing trend of the conversion curve becomes smoother, particularly for pressures of 40, 45, and 50 bar. Moreover, a substantial increase in the operation time required to reach 90% conversion is observed in Fig. 14(a) when increasing the pressure from 35 bar to 40 bar and from 40 bar to 45 bar, whereas a relatively smaller increase is noted when raising the pressure from 45 bar to 50 bar.

To facilitate a better comparison, Fig. 14(b) illustrates the relative increment (*RI*) of the batch operation time for every 5 bar pressure increase, calculated using the following equation:

$$RI = \frac{t(90\%)_{i+1} - t(90\%)_i}{t(90\%)_i} \times 100\% \quad (12)$$

where $t(90\%)$ represents the batch operation time required to achieve 90% conversion, and i denotes the simulated cases ranging from 20 bar to 50 bar in 5 bar increments. The results clearly display that increasing the pressure within the range of 20–50 bar extends the batch operation time to varying degrees. The most significant benefit is observed when increasing the pressure from 35 bar to 40 bar, yielding a 72.91% relative increment. However, beyond 45 bar, further pressure increases show a diminishing effect, with only a 9.02% increment from 45 bar to 50 bar. This suggests that the enhancement of ammonia synthesis via pressure increase weakens at higher pressures. Considering the trade-off of energy cost associated with pressure elevation, 40 bar is recommended as the optimal operating pressure for this reactor.

4.3.3. Temperature parametric study

Fig. 15 presents the results of the temperature parametric study, analyzing H_2 conversion and NH_3 absorbed fraction over time at four different temperatures: 250, 275, 300, and 325 °C. As shown in Fig. 15(a), higher temperatures significantly extend the high-conversion period. For instance, the >90% conversion threshold is maintained for 1482 s at 250 °C but extends to 4913 s at 325 °C, demonstrating a more than 3-fold increase in batch operation time with a 75 °C temperature rise. The critical time points for reaching 90% conversion are 2050 s for the 275 °C simulation case. However, after two hours of operation, the final conversion declines to 37.2%, 41.8%, 39.0%,

affecting reactor efficiency and increasing compression costs. Moreover, efficient thermal management represents a key challenge, as the exothermic nature of NH_3 synthesis combined with the endothermic desorption process during regeneration can cause nonuniform temperature profiles that impact both catalytic performance and sorbent stability. Material incompatibility issues between the metal halide sorbent and reactor internals must also be carefully evaluated to prevent corrosion or degradation under cyclic operation. Furthermore, repeated absorption-desorption cycles may induce structural fatigue or loss of capacity in the sorbent, reducing overall lifetime and operational reliability. More comprehensive models that capture and couple these phenomena should be developed to address these engineering aspects, e.g., fluid distribution, heat integration, material stability, and cyclic durability. Further investigations including more parametric studies are highly demanded for transitioning the sorption-enhanced NH_3 synthesis technology from conceptual modeling to industrial implementation.

5. Conclusions

This study presents a numerical investigation of ammonia synthesis with in-situ sorption enhancement from small to pilot scale. A transient CFD model was developed, validated against experimental data, and applied to analyze the dynamic behavior of the coupled synthesis-sorption process. The results demonstrate that the incorporation of sorbents not only stores the majority of the produced NH_3 but also significantly enhances the synthesis process, particularly with increasing numbers of catalyst-absorbent layers. In-situ NH_3 removal shifts the reaction equilibrium, enabling single-pass operation under mild conditions. A six-layer reactor achieves up to 66.8% higher H_2 conversion compared to non-sorptive cases, while a 60-layer pilot-scale reactor reaches over 90% conversion and 99.5% NH_3 capture within a 3676 s batch operation period. Parametric studies identify 300 °C and 40 bar as optimal operating conditions, balancing reaction performance, sorbent utilization, and operating time. At temperatures above 300 °C, however, the effectiveness of sorption enhancement declines significantly during later stages of operation.

Despite these promising results, several limitations of the present modeling study should be acknowledged. The CFD model assumes idealized conditions, neglecting practical factors such as sorbent degradation over multiple cycles and potential side reactions or corrosion effects that could impact long-term stability. Additionally, thermal gradients and nonuniformities associated with large-scale heat management were simplified. These factors, though beyond the current modeling scope, are critical for practical reactor design and will be addressed in future experimental and modeling investigations. Overall, these findings highlight the potential of sorption-enhanced configurations for flexible and sustainable NH_3 production across multiple scales, unlocking the role of NH_3 as a hydrogen carrier in the energy sector.

6. Future work

This work initiates the scale-up of sorption-integrated NH_3 synthesis under mild conditions, aiming to provide a pathway for decentralized green NH_3 production as a solution for hydrogen storage and transport. Nevertheless, further studies are required to address the limitations of this work and to tackle practical challenges such as material incompatibility and long-term durability. Future research directions include:

- Experimental validation and long-term performance testing of the pilot-scale reactor, including evaluation with alternative catalyst and absorbent materials together.
- Development and modeling of a regeneration strategy for sorbent reuse and NH_3 recovery, with attention to thermal degradation, corrosion, and potential NH_3 decomposition.

- Integration of the reactor into a full Power-to- NH_3 system with techno-economic evaluation and life cycle assessment.
- Comprehensive parametric study incorporating systematic variations in key parameters, supported by response surface analyses, to quantitatively reveal the interactions among conversion rate, sorption efficiency, and operation time.
- Optimization of practical operating strategies, including catalyst-to-absorbent ratios and space velocities, to enhance reactor flexibility and performance under dynamic conditions.

These efforts, together with contributions from the broader research community, will be essential for scaling up mild NH_3 synthesis with in-situ sorption. All data and models presented in this study are available upon request.

Nomenclature

Symbol	Explanation	Unit
a_i	Activity	[-]
C_2	Inertial loss coefficient	[-]
D_p	Particle diameter	[m]
E	Total energy	$\left[\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}}\right]$
h_i	Specific enthalpy	$\left[\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}}\right]$
J_i	Diffusive flux	$\left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^2 \text{ s}}\right]$
k	Rate constant	$\left[\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{m}^3 \text{ s}}\right]$
k_a	Equilibrium constant	[-]
k_{eff}	Effective thermal conductivity	$\left[\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m K}}\right]$
P	Pressure	[Pa]
R_{sorp}	Sorption reaction rate	$\left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{g}_{\text{MnCl}_2} \text{ min}}\right]$
R_{NH_3}	Synthesis reaction rate	$\left[\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{m}^3 \text{ h}}\right]$
S	Source term	[-]
S_m	Mass source term	$\left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3 \text{ s}}\right]$
S_h	Energy source term	$\left[\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^3}\right]$
X_A	Sorption capacity index	[-]
y_i	Mole fraction	[-]
α	Correction factor	[-]
α_p	Permeability	$[\text{m}^2]$
ε	Porosity	[-]
μ	Dynamic viscosity	$\left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m s}}\right]$
ρ	Density	$\left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}\right]$
$\bar{\tau}$	Viscous stress tensor	[-]
ϕ	Scalar	[-]

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Tianbao Gu: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Elizaveta Taranets:** Visualization, Validation, Software. **Hossein Asgharian:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Formal analysis. **Samuel Simon Araya:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation. **Fausto Gallucci:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources. **Vincenzo Liso:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Configuration data of the pilot reactor

No. sorbent bed	Bed volume (m ³)	Length (m)
Layer 1	5.31E-05	0.0777
Layer 2	5.26E-05	0.0769
Layer 3	5.17E-05	0.0757
Layer 4	5.09E-05	0.0742
Layer 5	5.00E-05	0.0732
Layer 6	4.89E-05	0.0716
Layer 7	4.80E-05	0.0702
Layer 8	4.70E-05	0.0688
Layer 9	4.59E-05	0.0672
Layer 10	4.49E-05	0.0657
Layer 11	4.39E-05	0.0642
Layer 12	4.29E-05	0.0627
Layer 13	4.18E-05	0.0611
Layer 14	4.07E-05	0.0596
Layer 15	3.97E-05	0.0581
Layer 16	3.86E-05	0.0564
Layer 17	3.75E-05	0.0548
Layer 18	3.64E-05	0.0533
Layer 19	3.54E-05	0.0516
Layer 20	3.43E-05	0.0502
Layer 21	3.32E-05	0.0485
Layer 22	3.22E-05	0.0469
Layer 23	3.09E-05	0.0453
Layer 24	2.97E-05	0.0439
Layer 25	2.86E-05	0.0425
Layer 26	2.75E-05	0.0412
Layer 27	2.64E-05	0.0396
Layer 28	2.52E-05	0.0378
Layer 29	2.41E-05	0.0352
Layer 30	2.29E-05	0.0335

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.152688>.

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